

**IMPACT OF ORGANIZATION FACTORS FOR THE
EMPLOYEE RETENTION IN XYZ LTD.**

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DECLARATION

I hereby certify that this report does not incorporate any material previously submitted for a degree in any university or institution to the best of my knowledge and it does not contain any material previously published or written by any other person except where due references is made in the text..

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Name of the Student

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Signature

Topic Confirmation

I hereby agreed to continue with the topic

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Name of the Supervisor :

Date :

Signature :

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Supervisor Certification

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Organization factors are one of the major determinants of employee retention in any organization. The purpose of this study was to determine the factors that can impact to the retention of production level staff of XYZ Ltd. The study was focus to identify the impact of organization factors for the employee retention purposes who are working at XYZ Company. Research for this report involved a review of current literature available regarding this problem and other factors identified, with the primary data being collected through a questionnaire.

The findings clearly indicate that supervisor support has the most significant effect on employee retention while learning and development provided to them as well as the image and recognition of their job among society too are factors that make them retain or leave. Income and benefits provided is always essential but is not the most significant is clearly proven by this study as well.

It is clear to us that reasons for poor retention will vary from person to person, but it is the duty of an employer to satisfy these employees as much as possible in order to retain the hard working and talented employees within the company. It is recommended that XYZ Ltd needs to continue add more value to their employees well being and development in the industry in order to increase their satisfaction levels and retain them in the company for longer periods of time.

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CHAPTER 01

INTRODUCTION TO THE STUDY

1.1 Introduction

XYZ PLC is an organization which is well reputed in Information Technology field in our country. As one of the best and most famous IT service provider in last few years in this trade. It is one of Sri Lanka's largest providers of IT solutions in the country. Anchored by a team of experienced and dynamic professionals, XYZ PLC offers a wide range of IT services that are of international standards.

Their vision is "Innovation through Excellence". Their mission is "To become a globally recognized and respected IT service provider that delivers "Best in Class" people, Who provides "Best of Bred" products and solutions through the leveraging of tomorrows technologies today". In order to fulfill this mission they follow a set of values inclusive of, excellence, by being excellent in everything they do, and being the best they can be. Another value in practice is "care", by fostering a great place to work through support for each other to reach and work with their full potential, while they provide a place for "innovation" by improving, reinventing and evolving constantly. A next value that is most important is the component of "trust" which they create through strong relationships between internal and external customers by being transparent in their dealings and providing convenience in every possible value. Another important value is to practice ethics and maintain integrity, by doing the right thing always. The competitive point for an organization is its people and the work load they carry out to achieve organizational objectives. Talented employees are thus considered the backbone of any successful organization.

Employers spend their money and time on recruitment and selection of talented peoples who are most suitable for their organization. Then they spend to induct them to fit into the culture of the organization. Finally they trained to improve their knowledge and skills so that they identify their tasks as to fulfill the objectives of the organization.

This study is framed to search about the relationship between retention of operational level employees and organization factors of XYZ PLC. According to scholars we can find out many factors that affect to the purpose of employee retention with any organization. For example stability of the job, working environment, opportunities for future jobs etc. scholars

have presented their view points on this, through their research and journal articles and books.

Govaerts et al (2011) mentioned various research has identified several factors relating to employee retention, situated on both organizational and employee levels. On the organizational side, factors influencing retention appear to be the existence of challenging and meaningful work, opportunities for advancement, empowerment, responsibility, managerial integrity and quality and new opportunities.

According to Allen, 2001; Behson, 2005; Casper & Buffardi, organizational work-life benefits and a supportive work climate are linked positively to employee well-being and retention and Work-life quality was found to be a significant predictor of job satisfaction, commitment and longer stays. Aryee et al. (1998) found a positive correlation between satisfaction with work flexibility and intentions to stay.

1.2 STATEMENT OF RESEARCH PROBLEM

According to the introduction of this study it is clear that there is an issue with retaining of employees in this company. Organizations have taken many actions to control this issue. All organizations are also identified the value of retaining employees. For control this some company have done with incentives, giving entertaining facilities and welfare activities etc. By giving all these, they expect only to retain people who recruited by them. Based on that, this research aims to identify the relationship between organization factors and retention of employees.

XYZ production staff is given the responsibility to support any kind of IT (Data Entry and Data Processing) work in the organization, for which they are paid a commission/Incentive according to the percentage of their monthly productivity carry out individually in addition to the basic salary they receive.

Khaled A. Ben-Bakr et al (1994) said that to avoid the business instability, it is always a challenge for organizations to keep their talented employees As cited in Das Lahkar Bidisha & Barua Mukulesh, Maertz & Campion (2013) has defined employee retention as relatively

less turnover research has focused specifically on how an employee decides to remain with an organization and what determines this attachment retention processes should be studied along with quitting processes. Cutler has stated that main demands on management in any organization are keeping motivated and dedicated human resources.

It is because keeping the employees rather than hiring is more important for success of the organization. Previous researchers such as Taplin et al. (2004), Amadasu (2003) and Gberevbie (2009) have established in their studies that employees will surely stay and work for the flourishing accomplishment of organizational goals if suitable employee retention strategies are adopted and implemented by organizations.

Acton & Golden added that retention of employees is not only important but retention of valued skills is more important. According to him, Human resource Department plays the dynamic role for retention of employees.

According to above literature most of researches have done with tangible aspects, which are directly related with retention matter, like salary or incentives, supervisory problems etc. but most of them did not focus about the organization culture. There for current researcher aims about how organization factors relate with employee retention. So In this review will be collected and analyzed quantitative data regarding organization factors and employee retention by distributing questionnaire. Sample will be taken from XYZ PLC.

1.3 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The conclusion of this study will be useful in creating strategies for employee retention. Under this theme today researcher identified its significance in three important aspects. Before policy with respect to the organization of the culture and employee retention is the inability to understand which surface which is necessary in order to develop. As well as it will be useful to understand, if you are there will be a change of the management or a change in thinking pattern, value system, just a change of the culture, it will have an effect on the preservation employee. And if the culture no sense to not make and what kind of solution could be to increase employee retention. And this research analyzes believed to why people continue to understand the reasons. This research analyzes supposed to understand the reasons why people bother about culture. As it gives the knowledge about the relationship between employee retention and organizational culture. The study also aimed to help the researcher to come up with useful recommendations. This study will help to identify new ways of thinking of employees. It helps to generate new ideas about how the culture has to change according to different behaviors of people.

1.4 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The organizational factors affecting retention of employees will be identified through a questionnaire distributed to ZYZ PLC production level employees selected at random. The study intends to find a relationship between these factors and how much they affect the maintenance of the target group of employees in the organization. The study is only in a few branches in the suburbs of Colombo, where this issue is significantly high especially due to be carried out administrative duties and audit purposes.

The research results cannot be generalized to the entire organization and there may be a completely different set of problems among employees in the branches of rural areas. Lack of time to select a small sample of the level of production employees from which conclusions are drawn. The research will be worth only as an honest opinion and the real thoughts of those workers forward without fear to put identified and punished. Although some confidence can be instilled their feedback are being put, if the researcher outsider to the organization finds it difficult to create a large component of trust and understanding between employees. The hectic workloads for some employees will also affect the answers they offer a number of

questions so they can get as soon as possible from the participation of the research. This also gives rise to a lack of precision facts that

In-depth interviews can be conducted with a number of employees of the sample, not every selected in the sample individual. Employees Perceptions vary due to the attitude and the behavior of employees. Therefore, only certain points of view can be understood. There is bias in the findings conclusions drawn up at the request of the questionnaire based on what the researcher thinks possible reasons for poor retention of its employees. The employee is not free to some details that they intend to communicate the full study to describe.

The study has many limitations, but it is worth spending some truth about this gradually growing problem of staff turnover problems know it has brought the chaos within the work environment.

1.5 Research Question

What are the organizational factors affecting for employee retention in XYZ PLC?

How to improve employee retention at XYZ company operational employees through organizational factors?

1.6 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1.6.1 General Objective

To recognize organizational factors affecting the operational level employee retention at XYZ Company.

1.6.2 Specific Objectives

To identify significance of the organizational factors towards retention of operational level staff at XYZ PLC.

To make suggestion to improve operational staff retention through organizational factors at the organization.

1.7 Organization of the Chapters

Chapter one : - Background of the problem, problem statement, objectives of the study,
Research questions, significance of the study

Chapter two : - Literature review, literature review from earlier studies.

Chapter three :-Research approach, Research strategy, Population of study, sampling
procedures
and sample size, data collection methods and data analysis methods,
Conceptual
framework and Hypothesis.

Chapter four : - Data presentation and analysis

Chapter five : - Conclusion findings and recommendation.

CHAPTER 02

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

Organizational factors play an important role in modern corporations where it generates a lot of benefits for the organization. This chapter is a collective presentation of the theoretical findings is highly relevant to this study as what organizational factors, Theories of organizational factors and employee retention and the importance of retaining employees in an organization. This literature has broken into a number of areas for ease of analysis. As deferent definitions on organizational factors, the importance of organizational factors, as well as scholars views on staff retention, and how it affects the organization and retention strategies used by organizations to keep their employees with them etc.

2.2 Important of Organizational Factors

A conceptual understanding of the organizational factor begins to have an understanding of why organizational factors are important to offer. Deal and Kennedy (1982) argued that organizations not only provide products and services, but also values and beliefs as well. Ultimately, a good understanding of the organizational factors can contribute to greater organizational effectiveness.

Sriramesh, J. Grunig, and Dozier (1996) states that "the effectiveness of the organization is the ultimate goal of most managers." (1983) analysis of the literature Smircich found that organizational factors are an important tool that can use strategic management to achieve organizational effectiveness.

According to Tichy (1982), organizational factors are complex and difficult to identify, but it has the broadest impact on the effectiveness of the organization Tichy used figurative analysis to reinforce the importance of organizational factors. He referred to the organization as a "strategic rope" consists of three intertwined strands together. Each strand represents what he identifies as key elements known as environments that affect an organization. The strands are technical, political and cultural.

Sun (2008) concluded that organizational factors should not be ignored "because the factors can be used as a competitive advantage in the organizational development". An organizational factors the beliefs and values are shared can also have benefits on a large scale with the collaboration, control, communications and engagement (Sun, 2008).

2.3 Employee Retention

Retaining talented employees is very important for managers because of the increasingly high rate of employee turnover. Now a day's business environment is very competitive therefore make and retain skilled workers, the key differentiator for most organizations. retention of staff is important because costly search candidate, and training time investments, expensive search candidate that are involved in it. Hence, it is not to maintain a key employee is a costly proposition for each organization. long-term health and success of any organization depends on the retention of key employees. For much satisfaction, organizational performance in terms of satisfied colleagues and reporting staff, increased sales, effective succession planning, etc., depends on the ability to retain the best employees in an organization. Encouraging employees to remain in the organization can be referred to for a long period of time as employee retention. It is the responsibility of every employer to retain their best employees. If they do not, they would be left without good employees. A good employer must know how to attract and retain employees. As a result of competition for scarce skills, is attracting and retaining quality employees emerged as the greatest challenge in human capital management. If an organization has not been able to maintain its employees, it will not be able to take advantage of human capital developed within the organization. When employers treat their employees like valued employees, they tend to improve in the organization (Frost, 2001) .It is therefore important that organizations keep their employees satisfied to maintain workers to stay. Many organizations are facing challenges in developing a strategy, staff retention, turnover rates are increasing in different organizations; if employees are unhappy with their bodies, they tend to leave the organization. This is a costly affair, especially when a valuable employee exits resulting in lost production. Moreover, the costs of recruiting other worker is very high and usually takes time. The responsibility lies with the employer to ensure that they have the right quality and quantity of employees in their organization.

2.4 Factors Affecting Employee Retention

Retention of staff is not affected by a single factor, but there are hosts of the factors that are responsible for the retention of staff in an organization. Management need to pay attention to factors such as Rewards, Supervision, Culture and Career Development. The mental dimension of retention of work characteristics, workers always prefer flexible working jobs where they can use their knowledge and see the results of their efforts, in turn, helps in the conservation of valuable resources. The social dimension includes the contacts that employees have with other people, both internally and externally. The physical dimension consists of working conditions and pay.

2.5 Rewards

According to Agarwal (1998) in the literature meaning of the word as a reward, "it's something that the ability of the organization to the workers in response to their achievements and contributions expected by the employees." That amount/price of wages or benefits for exchange to the services to provide workers to the organization. A reward is intrinsic or extrinsic, it may be in the form of money, ie bounces etc or reward can be in the form of recognition / certification, such commendation certificate or employee of the month, etc. In business environments rewards are offered in various forms, such recognition, cash bonuses, prizes, free travel and free merchandise etc. However, remuneration is the thing that has the organization in any form as a reaction to the contribution of the employee, the employees motivated to do well with to be positive behavior in the future. Silbert (2005) says that pay is very important because it lasting impression on employees and supports the perception of employees that they are valued.

Arthur (1994) & Huselid (1995) Organizations that are more committed to their employees are usually made more investments in comparison with similar organizations in progressive human resource practices, ie education, training & development and compensation package. These organizations also establish meritorious practices on remuneration distribution and distribution of the rewards more generous and fair. According to Walker (2001), compensation offer recognition, but non-monetary forms of recognition are not ignored and important. Davies (2001), Gold (2001) Recognition of bosses, team members, colleagues and

customers to enhance loyalty. employee participation in decision-making and influence the actions are also important.

Research studies have highlighted the link between pay and retaining workers (Watson Wyatt 1999 Tower Perrin, 2003; Mercer, 2003) and provides an insight into what to do workers, their words about the rewards and their feelings towards the work and remuneration issues. Recent studies on talent management also support assumption that good help and widely implemented remuneration practices in talent retention and management.

The annual survey of the "Watson Wyatt" on employee attitudes to the employer and the workplace, USA work in 2002, showed the opinions of 12,750 employees at all levels of employment in all major businesses, on different themes of work including rewards. The Watson Wyatt study found that the recognition is important for workers and they want to hear that their work followed recognized and appreciated.

2.6 Supervision

The leadership style treat affective factor in staff retention. The relationship between manager and employee play key role in the turnover of the intention of the workers. The organization "human face" is Supervisors. Leaders are the human face of the company. Eisenberger and colleagues (1990), suggested that view employees as regards the organization are strongly committed to their relationship with the manager. As supervisor support, open communication and a good relationship with the employee, the employee turnover intentions are less likely and more involved in the organization (Greenhaus, 1994). Leaders communicate as a band in order to execute the application between the expectations and the goals. By harmonizing the support rival claims supervisor and manage the indoor / outdoor environment. If the relationship between workers and managers exceed / strong workers will never try another new job opportunities rather than stay in the organization and vice versa. Employees leave the leaders no jobs so leader support is also essential in this respect. (Ontario, 2004)

Employees are valued and they feel valued actively participate in reducing the organization's goals, exhibit productive behavior, workplace and increased job involvement that absenteeism and turnover intention rates. The effective leadership style can be revealed

through formal and informal recognition. The workers' organizations responding to admire, support and encouragement, regardless of the environmental profession or personal (Silbert, 2005). For an accurate assessment of the performance management leader must ensure discuss progress with workers outside the time of the formal evaluation process. They help employees to find the right place in the company, not only move in the hierarchy next position (Freyermuth, 2007).

According Silbert (2005), well-trained and talented employees can easily find good job, position and work elsewhere; but to enhance effective way to preserve these talented staff is friendly and close working environment and to promote the leader support. Freyermuth (2007), recommended that the organization leader to support the workers must take care and to properly build the work environment where employees want to stay. Providing opportunities, testing their skills and provide the level of performance can improve the ability of workers and to keep them in the organization.

2.7 Culture

According to Logan (2000) studies have also indicated that staff retention could be affected by a number of important factors that must be carefully managed, such as organizational culture, compensation, strategy, policy and work life etc.

Previous research shows that a good recruitment strategy is the key to employee retention (Hascall, Hopkins and Hollman 1995). The yards should be realistic job preview unclear and unrealistic expectations lead to staff turnover. Organizational culture is very important for staff retention. Joan and Harris (1999) to see the organizational culture as more important than the job itself. While recruiting, the culture of a perfect fit for the staff should as far as possible will be leaving the organization misfit culture. Maintaining a healthy psychological contract is seen as a key strategy in retaining staff. Rousseau (1995) states that to be effective for retention strategies, it is important to manage the employee expectations. The psychological contract is aimed at workers subjective interpretations and evaluation of incentives and how they affect to remain on their intentions. Promoting and encouraging employee involvement is to maintain a strategy employed by organizations to their valued human capital.

Organizational Culture includes images seen in the direction of organizations, relationships between employees, the attitude towards customers and accepted way of performing tasks (Donald Catt and 1989). They note that, employees who are not likely to commit to the culture of an organization not to pursue employment in the company.

Joan and Harris (1999) emphasize the importance of organizational culture in staff retention and states that, in order to recruit and retain new employees Organizational culture is more important than the job itself. While recruiting, the culture of a perfect fit for the employee and must be presented to the employee as it is. Many employees tend to leave a company for misfit with the culture. She stresses that the first step in retaining workers is to ensure that the organization values clearly defined and integrated into the organization's vision, goals and strategy and communicated back and forth.

Sheridan (1992) in his study found that organizational culture was significantly related to performance and voluntary turnover.

Results of several studies Kreitner and Kinicki (1997) conclude that congruency between individual values and organizational values was significantly associated with intention to quit. Strong culture creates goal alignment, employee motivation and controls to improve organizational performance.

2.8 Training & Career Development

Investment is considered in employee training and career development as a key factor in retaining staff. Organization has the incentive to investment in the form of training & development only those employees whose organization expects to return and give the output to make his investment (Messmer, 2000). According to Clark (2001), organizations stepping up development for talented employees through skills analysis, effect on the interests of employees must develop and multisource assessment of the opportunities and formulate plans for action. Wetland (2003), suggested that businesses and individuals made investments in human capital in the form of training. Training improves the skills of employees. When employees are hired to improve the skill, organization needs to start training (Goldstein, 1991). According to Noe (1999), staff perception to new knowledge and skills they use at work, and also to gain share with other employees. Research studies found that the

organization often delayed training workers to establish workers personal value good matches with organizational or otherwise, so peter out employee turnover intention (Lauri, Benson with Cheney, 1996).

According to Gomez et al, (1995), training was gives specialized technology and skills of the employees and also helps to correct deficiencies in the performance of employees, while the development provide the skills and capabilities of employees who need the organization in the future. Developing the skill is to improve interpersonal communication, technological knowledge, problem solving and literacy etc. Garg & Rastogi (2006), explained that in today's competitive environment feedback is essential for workers' organizations and the more knowledge of the employee learn, the more he or she will perform and meet the global challenges of the market.

Bishop (1998), research on exercise showed that established, larger production and trade companies tend to provide staff training as multi-established companies with flexible production approach or high performance. Research study found that larger companies, high performance office and the organizations that spend more physical resources were generally more likely to retain their talent (Black and Lynch, 1996). Firms in the market with rapid technical progress and output progress more educated and those companies that faced no competitor in the last decade. According Frazis et al, (1998), companies that offer advantages over others, and train their employees through the adoption of innovative work practices.

Storey and Sisson (1993) suggest that training is a sign of organizational commitment to employees. Training also reflects the organization strategy that is based on reducing the value added in lieu of the cost. Leading companies in the industry recognized the extensive range of training, skills and career development are key factors in attracting and retaining the form of flexible, sophisticated and technologically employees that companies strategy to succeed in the computerized economy (Bassi and Van Buren, 1999 , Accenture, 2001).

CHAPTER 03

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

The chapter highlights the selection of what steps were used to identify the sampling technique whereby a sample is selected from the total population of the production level employees. The data collection methods, and an emphasis on each of the questions of the questionnaire, data presentation and analysis techniques are clearly defined by this section.

3.2 Research Approach

There are, Inductive and Deductive two types of surveys used. An inductive approach is collected the data and developed a theory as a result of the data-analysis. Whereas, if a hypothesis is being developed in research and deductive approach strategy is designed to check the hypotheses. There are five stages in the deductive approach: (Saunders et al, 2009), collecting a hypothesis, stating the hypothesis in operational terms, to test the hypothesis, exploring the outcome and the last will adjusting the hypothesis in the light of the outcome. The purpose of this contribution to the factors affecting the employees leave the organization and also evaluate maintain an appropriate approach to the workers in this sector surveys. It is the responsibility of the researcher to choose the most suitable research approach to evaluate this research. Design research is done to find the right answers to the proposed research (Cameron & Price, 2009). Therefore the researcher has adapted a deductive approach this study with respect to the factors that influence the retention and turnover of employees in XYZ PLC and the researcher assumes that there is sufficiently developed research in the field of conservation and provide sales employees employee.

3.3 Research Strategy

There are two method to research data; Quantitative and qualitative analysis. Qualitative data are non-numerical data that can occur in any form, such as opinions, beliefs, prospects, stories and pictures, and so on; or it can be defined as the expression of human experiences and opinions (Quinlan, 2011) which Quantitative data are numerical data or information collected will be calculated numerically. There are various methods of quantitative analysis, such as statistics, charts and diagrams that allow the researcher to calculate the data to be

more in the correct manner. The quantitative data analysis is to calculate from data using statistical techniques. The quantitative analysis is often based on the deductive approach. The collection of quantitative data highlighted in this study on the positivist method.

Therefore, this research is a quantitative strategy adapted by collecting information from employees of XYZ PLC. Quantitative analysis is a common research method and is expected to give positive results of the survey / questionnaire. This study's main method of quantitative approach will use the questionnaire. Questionnaire for ever and research and collect the large number of responses from the participants to analyze the data.

This research will attempt the researcher to use the most up-to-date, reliable and valid scale to the quantities based on the literature and research questions. There measure evidence of the work on this study, so it is designed literature present and more to concentrate the shortage of workers in the industry and the need to do more research.

3.4 Total Population

All survey data collect from the operational level employees of XYZ PLC Meegoda Branch. XYZ PLC Meegoda Branch consisted with around 300 employees.

3.5 Sample Size

Random method is use for selecting to the sample. By using sampling technique 85 are selected from the XYZ PLC Meegoda Branch.

Table selected population and the sample

	Population	Sample	Percentage
Operational Level Employees	300	85	28%

Table 3.5.1 Selected population and the sample

3.6 Sampling Technique

The technique of stratified clustered sampling was used to select the sample that about 28% of the total population.

Cluster sampling is achieved by dividing the population in groups are often geographically. These groups are referred to as clusters or blocks. The clusters are randomly selected and used in each element in the selected clusters.

Random sample was conducted by selecting a sample of 85 candidates only operational level workers, to whom a questionnaire consisting of an open ended question and four questions each of the four factors tested were carried out, were distributed. The comments and analyzes of the study is described in chapter 04.

3.7 Data Collection

The study based on the primary data which collect through questionnaire. It uses, for the purpose of measuring the impact of the organizational factors and the retention of operational level employees. The questionnaire is divided into four sections without Personal information section and Thank you note section.

Section 1 - The rewards employees receive

Section 2 - The supervision provided by the supervisor

Section 3 - The culture of the organization

Section 4 - The employee training and career development

Secondary data will be used from past research articles scholars and professionals and collected through the HR department of XYZ PLC.

3.8 Data Presentation and Analysis

This research focuses on the influence of organizational factors for the operational level employees working at XYZ PLC. Details of each individual employee collected and preserved response of each employee as an individual data source. Unit of analysis is the individual analyzes in this study.

The data were using the table notation stabbing method to calculate the number of responses for each of these 85 questions from questionnaires.

Subsequently, the data in the form of bar charts is was applied to have a pictorial view of the reactions.

Pie charts are used to analyze the percentage of quantities answers and comments made on each pie chart.

A scale was developed for the reactions and the hypothesis was tested using this scale in order to determine whether these factors have a direct impact on the conservation of the operational level employees in the company.

3.9 Conceptual Framework

The plan is to focus on a number of factors that influence the probability of the intention of the employees to be more than yet by the organization. These factors are the independent variables, while employee retention is considered more than three years as the dependent variable. The independent variables are Rewards, Supervision, Culture, Training and Career Development.

The relationship between these factors and the dependent variable of the poor retention of staff is under compared. The diagram summarizes the above facts vivid.

Figure 3.1 Conceptual framework of the study

3.10 Hypotheses

Ho1: There is no relationship between Rewards provided to the operation level staff and the retention of these employees in the organization.

Ha1: There is a relationship between Rewards provided to the operation level staff and the retention of these employees in the organization.

Ho2: There is no relationship between Supervision provided by the supervisors for operation level employees and the retention of these employees in the organization.

Ha2: There is a relationship between Supervision provided by the supervisors for operation level employees and the retention of these employees in the organization.

Ho3: There is no relationship between the organization culture and the retention of operation level employees in the organization.

Ha3: There is a relationship between the organization culture and the retention of operation level employees in the organization.

Ho4: There is no relationship between training and career development provided by organization to their employees and retention of operation level employees in the organization.

Ha4: There is a relationship between training and career development provided by organization to their employees and retention of operation level employees in the organization.

3.11 Limitation of the Study

This research is aimed at finding out the impact of the organizational factors and the preservation of the operational level employees. Therefore, researchers selected a sample of 85 employees of XYZ PLC. While the sample is limited to 85 people a limitation of this study. The researcher has chosen distribution questionnaire as data collection method; there is a possibility of re-gathering challenges of the questionnaire respondents.

CHAPTER 04

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Introduction

The study was conducted in order to establish the relationship / impact of organizational factors for the preservation of workers in XYZ PLC. Emphasis was put on four themes, namely the degree of employee satisfaction with the rewards. Next criterion which was tested was the aid of the regulator with respect to the success of each of these employees. The next was how organizational implications for staff retention target. To identify slot to hold career consequences for the employees.

The results obtained show a great number of trends that require to be emphasized in detail. This analysis will be useful to XYZ PLC to be the result of their efforts in the field of creating a great place to work and the job satisfaction of employees will understand forward. The results of primary importance for other organizations the strategies employed by this company to the high rate of turnover to minimize a common problem in the IT industry as much as possible with regard to the workers operating level in the company understand.

This chapter focuses on the findings of the empirical data presented using tables, bar graphs, pie charts and summarized explanation of the details on the charts.

A development of a scale was used for each of the satisfaction 4-1 in order to perform a calculation in order to test the hypothesis. Keys helps the researcher to bring the relationship between these variables and retaining employees.

The results of the analysis are further used by the researcher priority problems that contribute most and have the greatest effect retention of employees on the couch. Based on these issues, the researcher is able to management to provide clear recommendations on how these priority themes to be addressed to improve the purpose of maintaining the operation level employees.

4.2 Data Collection and Responding Rate

There are no rejected/uncompleted questionnaires all selected employees are successfully responding to all questions. So the response rate was 100% percent

4.3 Data Presentation

4.3.1 Summary Responses for Reward that Provide by the XYZ PLC

Table 4.3.1 Questionnaire responses of Section 01

Question Number	Response Type		No. of Response
S1 - Q1	Very Satisfied		13
	Satisfied		45
	Dissatisfied		24
	Highly dissatisfied		03
S1- Q2	Very Satisfied		06
	Satisfied		28
	Dissatisfied		40
	Highly dissatisfied		11
S1 - Q3	Very Satisfied		13
	Satisfied		40
	Dissatisfied		28
	Highly dissatisfied		04
S1 - Q4	Very Satisfied		05
	Satisfied		45
	Dissatisfied		29
	Highly dissatisfied		06
S1 - Q5	Very Satisfied		15
	Satisfied		53
	Dissatisfied		14
	Highly dissatisfied		03

Question 01

Figure 4.3.1 Response for Section 1 Question 01

Question 02

Figure 4.3.2 Response for Section 1 Question 02

Question 03

Figure 4.3.3 Response for Section 1 Question 03

Question 04

Figure 4.3.4 Response for Section 1 Question 04

Question 05

Figure 4.3.5 Response for Section 01 Question 05

4.3.2 Summary Response for Supervision Provided by the Organization

Table 4.3.2 Questionnaire response of Section 02

Question Number	Response Type		No. of Response
S2 - Q1	Very Satisfied		38
	Satisfied		42
	Dissatisfied		05
	Highly dissatisfied		00
S2- Q2	Very Satisfied		35
	Satisfied		39
	Dissatisfied		10
	Highly dissatisfied		01
S2 - Q3	Very Satisfied		34
	Satisfied		37
	Dissatisfied		13
	Highly dissatisfied		01
S2 - Q4	Very Satisfied		35
	Satisfied		43
	Dissatisfied		07
	Highly dissatisfied		01

Question 01

Figure 4.3.6 Response for Section 2 Question 01

Question 02

Figure 4.3.7 Response for Section 2 Question 02

Question 03

Figure 4.3.8 Response for Section 2 Question 03

Question 04

Figure 4.3.9 Response for Section 2 Question 04

4.3.3 Summery Response for Culture of Organization

Table 4.3.3 Questionnaire responses of Section 03

Question Number	Response Type		No. of Response
S3 - Q1	Very Satisfied		34
	Satisfied		41
	Dissatisfied		09
	Highly dissatisfied		01
S3- Q2	Very Satisfied		21
	Satisfied		45
	Dissatisfied		18
	Highly dissatisfied		01
S3 - Q3	Very Satisfied		11
	Satisfied		44
	Dissatisfied		26
	Highly dissatisfied		04
S3 - Q4	Very Satisfied		12
	Satisfied		43
	Dissatisfied		24
	Highly dissatisfied		06

Question 01

Figure 4.3.10 Response for Section 3 Question 01

Question 02

Figure 4.3.11 Response for Section 3 Question 02

Question 03

Figure 4.3.12 Response for Section 3 Question 03

Question 04

Figure 4.3.13 Response for Section 3 Question 04

4.3.4 Summery Response for Training and Career Development Provided by XYZ PLC

Table 4.3.4 Questionnaire responses of Section 04

Question Number	Response Type		No. of Response
S4 - Q1	Very Satisfied		38
	Satisfied		42
	Dissatisfied		05
	Highly dissatisfied		00
S4 - Q2	Very Satisfied		35
	Satisfied		39
	Dissatisfied		10
	Highly dissatisfied		01
S4 - Q3	Very Satisfied		34
	Satisfied		37
	Dissatisfied		13
	Highly dissatisfied		01
S4 - Q4	Very Satisfied		35
	Satisfied		43
	Dissatisfied		07
	Highly dissatisfied		01

Question 01

Figure 4.3.14 Response for Section 4 Question 01

Question 02

Figure 4.3.15 Response for Section 4 Question 02

Question 03

Figure 4.3.16 Response for Section 4 Question 03

Question 04

Figure 4.3.17 Response for Section 4 Question 04

4.3.5 Summery Response of the Period of Employment in XYZ PLC

Table 4.3.5

Period of Employment	No. of Responses
1 to 6 month	34
6 to 12 month	25
1 year to 3 year	24
More than 3 year	02
	85

Figure 4.3.18 Period of Employment

4.4 Data Analysis

4.4.1 Summary Analysis for Reward that Provide by the XYZ PLC

Figure 4.4.1 Analysis of response for section 01 question 01

It should be noted that nearly half of employees (53%) who have undergone the survey are satisfied with the remuneration they receive, while a significant 28% of workers are dissatisfied with the rewards they receive even their fundamental or other in order to meet required.

The research was conducted are carried out with a set of workers, ranging from those who have been with the company for more than three years to people who have been with the company for about 2 to 3 months. According to the duration could have given alter the responses of the employees stay, as a newcomer not when they will enter into the business a better income. Their income is 100% remuneration packages based on variable remuneration, which mainly will lead to maintain their displeasure as they will earn nothing at the beginning.

There is also a tendency that is displayed on the questionnaire feedback on staff members who was the organization for a longer period of time, i.e., more than 3 years. This group of employees is also of the opinion that the remuneration is insufficient. This suggests that these two groups of employees have left a greater tendency to the organization. The first criterion will be abandoned due to the fact that they do not earn enough to meet their basic needs,

while more experienced employees by competitors that can offer a better package for their knowledge and expertise to be used in their organizations seized.

The group of employees who have been in the market for a period of more than one year to do about five years enjoying the rewards they receive and have a positive attitude about having an opportunity to increase their income-based their desire and commitment to work.

Figure 4.4.2 Analysis of response for section 01 question 02

The second question of Part 1 was used to determine whether the reward received was sufficient to meet other needs, along with their basic needs. The pie chart clearly shows that to satisfy nearly 47% of workers are dissatisfied with the remuneration they receive for their other needs. About 13% are very very dissatisfied, giving rise to a total of 60% of employees who earn enough, which is just enough to meet their basic needs, but not for other needs care.

Satisfaction with pay also varies from person to person and how they want to live. There is a certain cluster of people who are satisfied with earning something instead of earning nothing. This is clearly observed with 33% of employees paid by the amount they receive. Although there is a group of people who desire to be more and more. Along this aspect, we can not limit to a measurement level from the amount of other needs that show hopes each individual. Hence, as an employer, more attention should be taken to the perception of the people and what levels they are at, so that pay packages are tailored to each individual employee of their capacity and the way in which they identify their stated goals.

The next question is trying to determine how workers compare with the amount of compensation they receive themselves, their peers and colleagues, and even their friends who have had similar level, but perhaps in other professions involved. The results are as follows:

Figure 4.4.3 Analysis of response for section 01 question 03

There is 47% of employees are satisfied with their pay compared to their friends and colleagues, while there is also a considerable amount of staff dissatisfaction (33%) and a 5% even those very dissatisfied. So accurately observed from the questionnaires that people belonging to the sector in which they have only been in the job market for a few months. There is an initial training period of 6 months; Therefore, this group of people is not in the field as soon as they put in the work, as they need to gain experience.

Hence, compared to their peers their income is very low or even zero, causing a feeling of low morale and dissatisfaction. these workers therefore remain less inclination. There is also a 15% of employees who are very satisfied with their earning rewards with regard to their friends. This group of people focused on the employees level of production that gives reacted with the company for over a year, while these workers very positively to the open ended question that this is a profession that requires a lot of commitment and dedication and sacrifice will be very high returns that can give unlimited high.

Figure 4.4.4 Analysis of response for section 01 question 04

The general attitude about the rewards they received was satisfactory with a majority of 53%, but there is also a group of 34% and 7% of workers sequentially dissatisfied and very dissatisfied. This group of people are the most critical was allowed to possess low motivation and a considerable amount in number. The majority of these people are school leavers, their social background, level of education makes their goals focused more monetary. So income is an important factor with which they retain the organization, as perceived by the investigation.

Figure 4.4.5 Analysis of response for section 01 question 05

The question about the degree of satisfaction with the pay / benefits they received received 62% of employees who undergo the examination to be satisfied, while another 18% are very

satisfied with what they might receive the achievement of certain objectives . This also shows that employees are fully aware of the facilities which they can achieve if they work hard and they understand the value of these facilities.

since these are the people who may be nearby scans to compare the pay / benefits they receive with other companies in the industry 16% of employees are dissatisfied can not be ignored if this group of people needs to be addressed more carefully, . It should also be noted that the majority of these workers only at the company for several months. This can also be up to the 16% of dissatisfied employees who are not yet certain targets are reached to the benefits they are entitled to receive long-term.

4.4.2 Summary Analysis for Supervision Provided by the Organization

The perception of their immediate supervisor almost all employees production is very satisfied at levels with a percentage of 45%, while the other 49% are satisfied with their boss, on the support which is fitted to them at the beginning of the job. This aspect of supervisor support is a remarkable best HR practice observed within the company as most employees do not leave people in the organization the organization itself, and that starts with their dissatisfaction with their immediate supervisor. The amount of training to line managers equipped to intervene in the organization as a good HR managers and leaders is evident in the spotlight of the comments of the employees.

Figure 4.4.6 Analysis of response for section 02 question 01

6% of employees are dissatisfied with their supervisor needs a lot of attention. Although this is only a significantly lower percentage, this fact shows that there are a number of promoters which can understand their roles. A team leader explained that the company provides a percentage of commission to them as one of the performance of their team member is high. Therefore, there is a benefit to the regulator to improve and develop their subordinates. The role of the regulator is not understood by some. Another aspect that a disgruntled crowd would be due to the attitude of some people who do not want to be led, but they prefer leaders from the start. There may be some of the production staff of this mentality, which the regulator would have considered unsupportive to be all the time.

The next question was aimed at obtaining feedback from employees who thought that the supervisor was supportive enough to show routes to increase their incentive which can improve their income within a short period of time. The responses clearly show that the line managers here had also been very successful to receive much gratitude as most employees had benefited from their supervisor to earn more for themselves equipped with the accompaniment. 41% of employees are very satisfied, while 46% are satisfied given the support.

Figure 4.4.7 Analysis of response for section 02 question 02

Here we see that a higher percentage than the initial help of the regulator is less. 12% of employees are dissatisfied with the poor attention given to them to improve their income. These are the employees who will not be retained by the organization, as they will be discouraged as she talks with their colleagues executives. Production workers would like to work under different supervisors because of this fact, and if this is not provided by the management of their last resort would be to not report to work. Hence, supervisor support especially in the area of improving the income of an individual must be addressed with greater attention. These are very sensitive areas where workers are demoralized

Figure 4.4.8 Analysis of response for section 02 question 03

The regulator also support the production staff have been doing their job. The company is more focused on the strategy of how to manage this level employees. staff so do exhibit a high degree of satisfaction with the support provided by the regulator.

It is pointed out during that out of this a lot of people that the survey has to undergo a certain degree of unsupportive supervisors. There is 15% of dissatisfied and 1% very dissatisfied employees who feel that they are not meant to be a good path. The tendency of these employees to leave the company is very high as they feel they need the guidance and direction of their boss to climb the ladder as their peers. These disgruntled employees clearly add up to the numbers that are lost in the society after orientation and introduced into the industry.

Figure 4.4.9 Analysis of response for section 02 question 04

Almost more satisfied than half of the employees on the general support of the regulator, in guiding and coaching them through their initial levels within the company. 41% are very satisfied that the ability of the team leaders that shows continued support for the new members of their team. 8% of workers dissatisfied was also emphasized in the above questions as members who would finally leave the organization due to the fact that they receive no support from their employers, and they do not like their superiors which they had to work.

4.4.3 Summary Analysis for Culture of the Organization

Figure 4.4.10 Analysis of response for section 03 question 01

Many of the employees seem to have a very positive attitude about the organization culture. 40% of employees who are very satisfied and 48% who are satisfied with the cultural factor associated with their work. This is very important for the preservation of every employee in an organization. This boost itself is usually what is needed for a company to thrive, as positivism in all employees in a workplace is what keeps it up and running.

Figure 4.4.11 Analysis of response for section 03 question 02

This question focus about in organization culture, employees has good society to compare their personal problems with other employees or management. 25% employees are very

satisfied with this question and 53% are satisfied. According to dissatisfied percentage of 21% and 1% we can realize that there is employees who have some personal problems. Management can focus this percentage and help them to solve their problems.

Figure 4.4.12 Analysis of response for section 03 question 03

Our society is such that we are more concerned about what others think about our workplace. Therefore, the next question focuses on how the employees feel that their friends, relatives and neighbors think their organization's culture. Over the road, the renowned company plays an important role with regard to this reaction, in my opinion. About 52% of employees satisfied while about 13% responded to be very happy when their friends think of the workplace culture.

30% of employees who responded with dissatisfaction clearly shows the standard of our people. Our friends, brothers and sisters are only happy to recognize us only if we are ranked in high positions. The pressure is created within an employee as a result of this fact about how they recognized among their relatives, friends, and neighbors who we see every day, will also face a number of these workers to the task want something more acceptable leave other people. Therefore, the tendency to retain employees is also evident on the basis of what this job and the organization within our circle of people we come in contact created every day.

Figure 4.4.13 Analysis of response for section 03 question 04

This question focused what employee think about their future with this organization. 14% percent and 51% percent satisfy their future with XYZ PLC. But other 28% percent and 7% percent count are not satisfied. This none satisfy peoples have negative idea about this company and it will be a pressure to satisfy count, it will drive employees mind to retention purpose.

4.4.4 Summery Analysis for Training and Career Development Provided by XYZ PLC

Figure 4.4.14 Analysis of response for section 04 question 01

The employees who underwent the study are very satisfied or satisfied (48%, 51%) with the knowledge that they had about the IT industry when they joined. This shows the high levels

of training provided to employees when they join the company. The cost of the company's all get lost leaving many employees with the knowledge they get from the organization about the industry at the beginning of their careers.

Figure 4.4.15 Analysis of response for section 04 question 02

Half of the employees who are undergoing investigation satisfied with the knowledge that they compete on the company and other organizations in the market. The clarity with which the organization is trying to provide the employees about what they competition is evident in the level of satisfaction is very high. There is only 2% of employees who are not happy knowledge on the condition that they may be ignored by the large number of responses received with satisfaction the information they have about the organization.

Figure 4.4.16 Analysis of response for section 04 question 03

The product received training new employees must be exceptionally well as the majority of the reactions on the level of very satisfied and satisfied criteria approach to about 88% total. There are also 16% of employees are dissatisfied with the training. These employees can more experienced person who would have found a lot of other important aspects that can be exposed to newcomers during a training session. Therefore, to obtain their expertise is an added advantage for the company.

Figure 4.4.17 Analysis of response for section 04 question 03

The overall satisfaction with the learning they receive from the company is satisfied and very satisfied levels sequentially 46% and 52%. Therefore, on the side of the business, their focus on being a learning organization is also highlighted by the degree of satisfaction of the majority of workers on their journey to the insurance industry.

4.5 Hypothesis Test

A scale was developed for the response levels as follows.

Response	Value
Very Satisfied	4
Satisfied	3
Dissatisfied	2
Highly Dissatisfied	1

$$\text{Highest value of the series} = 85 \times 4 = 340$$

$$\text{Lowest value of the series} = 85 \times 1 = 85$$

$$\text{Range} = 340 - 85 = 255$$

$$\text{Quadrant value} = 255 / 4 = 63.75$$

Ho1: There is no relationship between Rewards provided to the operation level staff and the retention of these employees in the organization.

Ha1: There is a relationship between Rewards provided to the operation level staff and the retention of these employees in the organization.

Section 01	Values	Total
Question 01	$(13 \times 4) + (45 \times 3) + (24 \times 2) + (03 \times 1)$	238
Question 02	$(06 \times 4) + (28 \times 3) + (40 \times 2) + (11 \times 1)$	199
Question 03	$(13 \times 4) + (40 \times 3) + (28 \times 2) + (04 \times 1)$	232
Question 04	$(05 \times 4) + (45 \times 3) + (29 \times 2) + (06 \times 1)$	219
Question 05	$(15 \times 4) + (53 \times 3) + (14 \times 2) + (03 \times 1)$	250
Total		1138

$$\text{Average} = 1138/5 = 227.6$$

Ha1 accepted. It is proved there is a relationship between Rewards provided to the operation level staff and the retention of these employees in the organization.

Ho2: There is no relationship between Supervision provided by the supervisors for operation level employees and the retention of these employees in the organization.

Ha2: There is a relationship between Supervision provided by the supervisors for operation level employees and the retention of these employees in the organization.

Section 02	Values	Total
Question 01	$(38 \times 4) + (42 \times 3) + (05 \times 2) + (00 \times 1)$	288
Question 02	$(35 \times 4) + (39 \times 3) + (10 \times 2) + (01 \times 1)$	278
Question 03	$(34 \times 4) + (37 \times 3) + (13 \times 2) + (01 \times 1)$	274
Question 04	$(35 \times 4) + (37 \times 3) + (13 \times 2) + (00 \times 1)$	284
Total		1124

$$\text{Average} = 1124/4 = 281$$

Ha2 is accepted. It is proved there is a relationship between Supervision provided by the supervisors for operation level employees and the retention of these employees in the organization.

Ho3: There is no relationship between the organization culture and the retention of operation level employees in the organization.

Ha3: There is a relationship between the organization culture and the retention of operation level employees in the organization.

Section 03	Values	Total
Question 01	$(34 \times 4) + (41 \times 3) + (09 \times 2) + (01 \times 1)$	278
Question 02	$(21 \times 4) + (45 \times 3) + (18 \times 2) + (01 \times 1)$	256
Question 03	$(11 \times 4) + (44 \times 3) + (26 \times 2) + (04 \times 1)$	232
Question 04	$(12 \times 4) + (43 \times 3) + (24 \times 2) + (06 \times 1)$	231
Total		997

Average = $997/4 = 249.25$

Ha3 is accepted. It is proved there is a relationship between the organization culture and the retention of operation level employees in the organization.

Ho4: There is no relationship between training and career development provided by organization to their employees and retention of operation level employees in the organization.

Ha4: There is a relationship between training and career development provided by organization to their employees and retention of operation level employees in the organization.

Section 04	Values	Total
Question 01	$(41 \times 4) + (43 \times 3) + (00 \times 2) + (01 \times 1)$	294
Question 02	$(29 \times 4) + (42 \times 3) + (12 \times 2) + (02 \times 1)$	258
Question 03	$(27 \times 4) + (48 \times 3) + (10 \times 2) + (00 \times 1)$	272
Question 04	$(44 \times 4) + (39 \times 3) + (01 \times 2) + (01 \times 1)$	296
Total		1120

$$\text{Average} = 1120/4 = 280$$

Ha4 is accepted. It is proved there is a relationship between training and career development provided by organization to their employees and retention of operation level employees in the organization.

According to the numerical analysis and testing of the hypothesis is also further evidence that all factors tested above important in retaining employees of production levels in the organization.

The factors can be prioritized as,

- The Reward and other benefits received
- The support, supervision provided by supervisor and managers
- The culture of the company
- The training and career development provided by company

The apparent results of the analysis that HR related issues which should be addressed directly to see that employees are happy and committed to work for an organization of which they receive a general support for their future.

CHAPTER 05

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Introduction

This final chapter presents the whole study summary and conclusions based upon the past discussions, an additionally this chapter discuss the recommendation and suggestion for future research who hope to research in this topic.

5.2 Summary of the Findings

There were two specific research objectives in this research. First is identify significance of the organizational factors towards retention of operational level staff at XYZ PLC. Second one is making suggestion to improve operational staff retention through organizational factors at the organization.

According to data analysis it is proved there is a relationship between organizational factors and employee retention of operational level staff members. There for when organization make decisions it is well needed to be sensitive regarding organizational factors. The factors we identified make positive impact on employee retention in the organization. The selected factors are, Reward, Supervision, Culture, Training and Career Development, We can identify using pie charts how much these factors impacting to the employee retention in this company.

5.3 Conclusion

The investigation of the grounds of production level XYZ PLC to the storage of the workers tested indicates that all the four factors. The factors are the rewards they have the support of the supervisor to employee jobs, the culture of the organization, training and career finally received by the company.

It can also be concluded that if these issues prioritized been proven performed according to the numerical analysis which is more than the monetary benefits of work, employees are

more interested in the career they receive, and the organizational culture that they face every day.

Retain people or leave jobs if they can not get along with their supervisors is a recognized fact. This study also elaborates this factor very effective because most of the staff are to lead given by their supervisors for their growth in the industry and they are very happy about this fact.

Finally, it can be concluded that this study sheds light on how an alert and effective HR team should be to establish among the people promoting these issues. They should be tailored to corrective action or device to take preventive measures to prevent the amount of the reduction in the workforce. This is a direct cost to the company and thus leads to disruption of the functioning of the organization and the intended goals of the organization inaccessible.

5.4 Recommendations

XYZ PLC has a lot of efforts to improve employee satisfaction, so that their needs are catered for and they will remain happy with the company taken for a long time. Yet they seem to experience high turnover related to the employee level production sector. To the task of minimizing the poor employee retention a systematic approach to key issues and contribute needed to reach. The following recommendations can be used presented, as determined by the study.

1. Examine and improve the recruitment and screening process

The responses of the survey shows that some of these employees have joined the organization due to various reasons such as, unable to close any other trade because not age or their qualifications are not enough, or because of a lack of experience . Hence the selection processes are not able to these individuals who will bring some additional costs to identify the long-term organization.

Therefore it is necessary to identify the individual attitude to a job, reducing the amount of involvement that can be expected from this former employees. Attitude testing of various sizes will be needed to determine whether these people have a passion for this service to carry out related tasks, whether they want a supervisor who

tolerate them in the first place and whether they are actually capable of a high pressure will coach to listen and face many challenges targeting is very common in this industry.

There is also a need to raise the level of the responsibilities of this individual to their family, parents, etc. Many of these sales to retain staff to identify due to the amount of income they earn if they work hard. The employees have said that this is a job where one is able to increase their income unlimitedly if they are willing and committed to do that. With the amount of responsibilities, if they do not ways and means to get money if they desired dissatisfied. Hence their goals are recognized in the selection process can help determine how the sales targets to these people, so their objective as well as the organizational goal can be achieved can be attributed. This can be carried out by simple questions such as “how many siblings are you responsible for?” “How many children do you have?” “Who else earns for the family?” etc.

2. Revise training sessions

There is a comprehensive training to all levels of the production staff at the beginning of the workout. Even with all this additional training offered determine the answers to the questionnaire that the amount of training on other products in the market and the training of the IT industry (KPO / BPO) has been insufficient. This is the reaction of many of the manufacturing members that the company had more than 3 years in the business. This shows that many changes to the programs that are held to be performed. In my opinion I think it is necessary to have a session where the sales staff who had been in the field for an extended period of time should be brought up to share their experiences with their colleagues on what actions they took to with difficult situations include. Training can be made more effective through these methods and a newcomer is able to capture the true essence of a quality education through these methods. Then they are more equipped to very effectively overcome problematic situations.

3. Introduce more supervisor training

It is also necessary to note that some reactions show that workers are dissatisfied with their leadership due to many reasons. Some of these are that they are not supportive of the production chain, some were not even useful to build their way once they have

joined, while there was not shown dissatisfaction employees different ways to increase their income. This can not fully blame the regulator, but these symptoms can go a long way to creating a group of employees to come up with this mind set the time, so they leave the organization. Therefore it is necessary to emphasize to managers that they need a good HR managers, and in the treatment of these workers depend solely on them as they enter the trade line. This will enable more employees to spread the good word among their peers and create a friendly environment where supervisor subordinate relationships are non-hostile, with staff retention can be improved.

4. Introduce Personality development programs

The attitude among society about Data Entry Operator (production level staff) is very poor. This is because the majority of those representatives will not dress well, not express eloquently and be humble at times. Therefore, to change the image of an output member. This change can only be done by the employees themselves.

Therefore, the company should try to help them by involving them in many courses the way they talk and dress can improve and socialize in society. The social image is seen as a major impact on workers like o change their work because of the lack of recognition and acceptance in society among friends and family.

Therefore it must be noted that many resolutions need to be still implemented in order to prevent the retention of employees at XYZ PLC.

5.5 Limitations of the Study and Directions for Further Research Area

The researcher had to face many limitations during the study and would like to suggest the following aspects which will help the future researchers to carry out their future research very well. The outcome will also be improved. This study is considered only 85 operational level employees of XYZ PLC. This may reduce the reliability of this research. Responses can be change according to the situation and mental conditions at the time of collecting data and respondents may fear to give real facts. The findings will be applicable only for selected employee category only. And the findings may not derive whole idea about the entire sector because this study limited only to one organization in the entire industry.

LIST OF REFERENCES

- Acton, T., Golden, W.(2003). *“Traning the knowledge worker: A descriptive study of training practices in Irish software companies”*. Journal. Eur.Ind. Train, 27(4):137-146.
- Agarwal, N.C. (1998). *“Reward Systems: Emerging Trends and Issues”*. CanadianPsychology, 39(1), 60-70.
- Bassi, J. L., & Van Buren, M. E. (1999). *“Sharpening the Leading Edge”*. Training and Development, 53 (1), 23-31.
- Black, Sandra E., Lisa M. Lynch, and Anya Krivelyova. 2004. *How workers fare when employers innovate*. Industrial Relations 43 (1): 44–66.
- Clarke, K.F. (2001). *What businesses are doing to attract and retain employee- becoming an employer of choice*. In Employee Benefits Journal.pp. 34-37.
- Davies, D., Taylor,R., Savery, C (2001). *“The role of appraisal, remuneration and training in improving staff relations in the Western Australian accommodation industry: A comparative study”*. Journal of European Training, 25 (6/7). 366-373.
- Eisenberger, R., Fasolo, P., & Davis-LaMastro, V. (1990). *“Percieved organizational support and employee diligence, commitment, and innovation”*. Journal of Applied Psychology, 75, 51-59.
- Frazis, H., Gittleman, M., Horrigan, M. and Joyce, M. (1998). *Results from the 1995 survey of employer provided training*. In Monthly labour review.21 (6): 3-14.
- Freyermuth (2007), —*Retaining Employees in a Tightening Labor Market*ll, RSM McGladrey.
- Garg, P. & Rastongi, R. (2006). *New model of job design motivation employees Performance*. Journal of Management Development.
- Goldstein, I.L. (1991). *Training in work organizations*. In M.D. Dunnette and L.M. Hough (Eds.) Handbook of industrial and ort:anizational psychology, Volume 2, 507-620. Palo Alto, CA: Consulting Psychologists Press.

Greenhaus, J. H. & Callanan. G. A. 1994. *Career Management*. The Dryden Press, Fort Worth, Texas.

J. Arthur (1994), —*Effects of Human Resource Systems on Manufacturing Performance and Turnover*, Academy of Management Journal, Vol. 37, Pp. 670–687.

J. Delaney & M. Huselid (1996), —*The Impact of HRM Practices on Perception of Organizational Performance*, Academy of Management Journal, Vol. 39, Pp. 949–969.

J.W. Walker (2001), —*Perspectives*, *Human Resource Planning*, Vol. 24, No. 1, Pp. 6–10.

John E. Sheridan, (1992). *Organizational Culture and Employee Retention*. The Academy of Management Journal.

Kreitner, R., & Kinicki, A. (2001). *Organizational behavior (5th ed.)*. Boston: Irwin/McGraw-Hill.

Mercer Report, (2003). *Mercer study raises red flags for employer pay and benefits plans (findings of the 2002 people at work survey)*. In human resource department management report. pp. 8-15.

Messmer, M. (2000). *Orientations programs can be key to employee retention*. In *Strategic Finance*. 81 (8):12-15.

Rousseau D.M., (1995), *'Psychological Contracts in Organisations'*, Sage Publications, California, USA.

Silbert, L.T. (2005). *The effect of Tangible Rewards on Perceived Organizational Support*. Management Sciences.

Storey, J. 1992. *Developments in the Management of Human Resources*. Oxford: Blackwell.

Watson, Wyatt. (1999). *Work USA 2000: Employee commitment and the bottom line*. Bethesda, MD: Watson Wyatt. pp: 43-58.

APPENDIX

THE QUESTIONNAIRE USED FOR THE STUDY

Dear Participant,

Based on the studies performed by the scholars and professionals there is a considerable impact of organizational factors on retention of employees. Therefore this study is being performed to identify the relationship between organizational factors and its impact for the retention of operational level employees based on the data collected through the category of operational level staff members at XYZ PLC, Meegoda Branch.

Researcher,

It is assured that the information provided by the participants by no means be used for the purposes other than the study.

Identification

1. Age category

- a. Below 20 years
- b. 20 – 25 years
- c. 25 – 30 years
- d. Above 30 years

2. Gender

- a. Male
- b. Female

3. Experience in XYZ PLC

- a. 1 to 6 months
- b. 6 to 12 months
- c. 1 to 3 years
- d. More than 3 years

Section 1 - The rewards employees receive

Please put a tick (✓) to select your answer.

		Very Satisfied	Satisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly dissatisfied
Q1	I am satisfied with the salary scale of the month				
Q2	I am satisfied with the level of incentives of the month				
Q3	I happy with medical facilities company provide to me				
Q4	Satisfaction on other benefits other than the salary				
Q5	I am satisfy with the organization reward system				

Section 2 - The supervision provided by the supervisor

Please put a tick (✓) to select your answer.

		Very Satisfied	Satisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly dissatisfied
Q1	The supervisor's support when you started the job				
Q2	The supervisor support to improve your income				
Q3	The supervisor support for continue your job				
Q4	The overall support and guidance by the supervisor				

Section 3 - The culture of the organization

Please put a tick (✓) to select your answer.

		Very Satisfied	Satisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly dissatisfied
Q1	The organization has clear business and operational objectives that are understood by all employees				
Q2	Employee feel comfortable talking about personal issues with other employees and management				
Q3	Most employees would speak very positively about the company				
Q4	Employee feel confident and certain about the organization's future				

Section 4 - The employee training and career development

Please put a tick (✓) to select your answer.

		Very Satisfied	Satisfied	Dissatisfied	Highly dissatisfied
Q1	Adequate knowledge was provided about the IT industry				
Q2	Adequate knowledge was provided about the company and their competitors				
Q3	Adequate knowledge was provided about the services of the company and the services of competitors				
Q4	Overall satisfaction on training and career development provided by the company				

Dear Participant,

I highly appreciate your kind cooperation for providing your valuable ideas for this as I will use these to successfully complete my thesis. Thank you very much for your support.

Researcher
P.G.R.C. Rathnayake